

Implementation of multi-objective production scheduling in the dynamic environment of the flat steel industry

E. Sirovnik, C. Schirm, D. Müller, thyssenkrupp Rasselstein GmbH, Germany; M. Rabe, TU Dortmund University, Germany; J. Brandenburger, A. Rajabi, A. Wolff, VDEh-Betriebsforschungsinstitut, Germany; J. Ordieres, M. Gutierrez, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Spain; V. Colla, V. Iannino, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna; Italy; A. Maddaloni, Télécom Sud Paris, France

Contact data

Erwin Sirovnik, thyssenkrupp Rasselstein GmbH, Koblenzer Str. 141, 56626 Andernach (Germany), +49 (0) 2632 3097 2447, erwin.sirovnik@thyssenkrupp.com

Summary

The European flat steel industry has come under immense competitive pressure as a result of globalization. To retain its market position, costs must be further reduced and unique selling points, such as quality, further expanded. A contribution to these requirements can be provided by an advanced production scheduling in a flexible flow production, without the need for an investment in capital-intensive plant components. Within the EU-funded RFCS project DynReAct, a scheduling approach is under development to generate optimized production plans for each individual coil at each production step considering real-time plant information. This concept offers immediate reactions to critical situations like insufficient plant performances or coils that are off the quality specifications. The optimal routing and sequencing will be estimated using real-time-capable plant performance models derived from machine learning on large historical data, which will be incorporated in multi-objective optimization methods. This approach enables the associated complexity to be mastered and other factors, such as quality, energy, or maintenance, to be taken into account in scheduling in addition to the classic logistical targets. In this work, the concept of multi-objective production scheduling is presented by the necessary foundations for the implementation in a practical use case in the tin plate industry.

Key Words

Multi-objective production scheduling, plant performance models, flat steel industry, hybrid approach

Introduction

In the course of globalization, the competitive pressure on the European flat steel industry is continuously increasing, posing various challenges that need to be overcome in order to retain and, ideally, improve the market position. Digitalization plays a key role in this context and opens up new opportunities. It provides a multitude of technologies to increase production efficiency with cost and resource savings, achieving higher product quality, maximizing plant performance, and planning a flexible production [1]. On this train of thoughts, efforts to increase data availability and transparency are on the rise, and one of the greatest benefits is to be found in production planning [2] and scheduling based on process data.

Multi-objective production scheduling and plant performance models

A valuable contribution to these requirements can be achieved by an advanced production scheduling in a flexible flow production, without the need for an investment in capital-intensive plant components. Within the EU-funded Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS) project DynReAct, a scheduling approach is under development to generate optimized production plans for each individual coil at each production step considering real-time plant information. This concept enables immediate reactions to critical situations like insufficient plant performance or coils that are outside the quality specifications. The optimal routing and sequencing will be estimated using real-time-capable plant performance models derived from machine learning on large historical data, which will be incorporated in multi-objective optimization methods. This approach enables the associated complexity to be mastered and other factors, such as quality, to be taken into

account in scheduling in addition to the classic logistical targets.

The aim of this work is to provide the preparatory basis for the implementation of a multi-objective scheduling on a practical use case in the dynamic environment of the flat steel industry. This production scheduling approach was developed based on the use case of a tinplate production at the thyssenkrupp Rasselstein GmbH, which includes the following main production stages:

Pickling: The starting material for the production of packaging steel is hot-rolled steel strip. The scale produced during hot rolling is removed in a continuous pickling line.

Cold rolling: In the cold rolling process, high rolling forces are transmitted to the strip via support and work rolls, bringing the coil to the required thickness.

Degreasing and annealing: During rolling, the thickness of the strip is often reduced by more than 90 percent. The work hardening that occurs must be reversed by a recrystallizing annealing process after the strip has been cleaned of impurities resulting from an upstream degreasing process.

Temper rolling: To give the strip the required forming properties, re-rolling, also known as temper rolling, takes place after annealing.

Finishing: The strip enters a tin-containing electrolyte in the tinning lines, where it is passed as a cathode between two rows of tin anodes. With the aid of the electric current, the tin of the anodes is dissolved and deposited on the strip. By subsequently heating the strip above the tin melting point and quenching in water, the brilliant shine is achieved. Special chromium-plated sheet is also produced in a process similar to tinning.

Since the finishing lines represent the highest complexity of alternative actions in the context of scheduling and offer the largest input of available process data, this production stage was selected as the focus for the plant performance models.

For the present use case, three different promising scheduling approaches were compared with each other. The results demonstrate that each method has its own specific advantages and disadvantages. It turns out that they complement each other excellently instead of competing. Thus, preference for a hybrid solution is the result of this comparison and, in consequence, a planning pyramid (Figure 1) with three different levels is created [3]:

Figure 1: Planning pyramid

Long-term planning (decomposition approach based on continuous flow model): In this order-less approach for the long-term horizon, the planning problem is simplified to a reasonable level. Hence, a manufacturing system can be approximately represented by a time-continuous or time-discrete dynamic model. The development of a dynamic model of a manufacturing system requires the definition of state (inventory at each production stage) and control variables (production). Besides, the capacity constraints are also considered in this model. The formulated continuous scheduling problem is an optimal control problem with state constraints, and this can then be calculated in a rendering horizontal scheme [4]. Different production routes of the relevant product groups can be taken into account in this mass flow method. At this level, the user can use these options to plan capacities and coordinate the product portfolio to be produced.

Mid-term planning (multi-objective mixed-integer linear programming-based approach): This approach is a combination of Multi-Objective Optimization (MOO) techniques with a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) formulation. It provides a preliminary global optimal resource scheduling under static conditions, i.e., based on production orders and coils and not considering unexpected events [3]. MILP techniques have the advantage that they can be used for a wide range of applications to provide optimal solutions. However, the techniques require high computation time, which is a disadvantage that makes dynamic scheduling for continuous production difficult. To reduce the computation time, a complexity reduction of the optimization problem has been integrated. With this tool, the user can create plans regarding the routing and sequencing of released orders as well as coils.

Short-term planning (auction-based multi-agent approach): The auction-based multi-agent scheduling system is predestined for uncertain scheduling environments regarding resource availability and is characterized by its responsiveness, flexibility and robustness. On a negotiation platform, different agents represent production facilities, the coils to be

produced, and auxiliary agents. Thereby, coils can bid on different auction processes at each resource with an available virtual budget depending on their status. Concerning the lowest virtual costs, the utility maximization of each resource agent is balanced with the coil agent's objective. This approach acts towards the user as an adviser and delivers robust reaction strategies based on real-time process data.

This hybrid approach is expected to improve robustness and transparency of the production planning results considering a global production strategy [3].

Key performance indicators (KPIs), which are determined by aggregating information, are used for the overall management of production. They describe the overall performance of production and are focused on decision makers on the management level. If these KPIs were extended to include the ability to consider real-time manufacturing events and data, a holistic description of production performance could be provided from the operator on the line to the plant manager. In a broader sense, this means that real-time events must be considered in addition to transactions (e.g., balanced scorecard).

In a production with several production stages, each plant pursues its own individual goals, which make their own contribution to maximizing performance. This is due, for example, to the different characteristics of the plants, their respective semi-finished products or the corresponding processing methods. While some of these characteristics are fixed (e.g., construction-related), others are highly dynamic, difficult to specify, or even dependent on the coil to be processed (e.g., selected quality characteristics). As a result of this implied complexity, a deep analysis of historical data was performed to build a robust plant performance model with real-time prediction using supervised as well as unsupervised learning in combination with expert domain knowledge. These predicted plant performance targets are to be processed in the scheduler. The previous selection of targets should be performed with utmost care in the light of the multi-objective optimization problem as well as the curse of dimensionality and the associated combinatorial explosion.

In this practical use case, real-time plant performance models were developed for forecasting the following three dimensions at the various finishing plants:

Quality performance dimension: For the plant performance model regarding quality, the use case of very sensitive products was taken. These materials are packaging materials that are in direct contact with

dry foods such as milk powder and require a very bright surface. Small defects in the surface or any contaminants will cause the filling material to stick to the cans and cause quality control to fail. One of the main reasons for this quality problem are spots on the material surface coming from the production process. These products are produced on all tinning lines. In the present use case, the aim is to apply data analysis techniques to automatically identify these relevant spots at an early stage in order to reduce or avoid the associated quality defects via rescheduling. The necessary surface data are supplied by automatic surface inspection systems from the production process. By applying the multi-scale data representation model presented in [5], the positions of surface defects detected during production can be investigated with other product and process information and placed over multiple coils by aggregation. With respect to the online identification of suspect defect distributions, a deep embedding clustering (DEC) [6] developed for industry applications was selected to perform this clustering task and trigger the impulse for appropriate rescheduling strategies in given cases.

Energy performance dimension: In the plant performance model for energy, the focus was placed on electrical energy, as this represents the main part of energy consumption at the finishing plants. The individual energy consumptions are collected online across all relevant components of each finishing line and linked to the accompanying material-piece-related production data for exploratory data analysis. This ensures the allocation of energy consumption per coil and order. In a first analysis, the individual features of the production data were examined with respect to their relevance for the variability of energy consumption at the individual finishing plants. Energy consumption over strip length was found to be the basis for measuring this energy dimension. This allows the effects of rescheduling measures or quality problems on this target variable to be recorded. A model based on the random forest approach [7] was developed to predict the energy consumption of a coil on a selected finishing line.

Maintenance performance dimension: For the finishing lines, the maintenance dimension refers to the mileage of each roll before it needs to be replaced. A finishing line contains over 100 different rolls performing different technical tasks. In a first stage, the historical data of the individual rolls was examined. By combining a linear model with decision trees, it is possible to define individual rules to predict the performance of the rolls.

Conclusion

With the scheduling procedure and the plant performance models, the two basic pillars for the

implementation of multi-objective production scheduling in the dynamic environment of the flat steel industry were presented using a practical example. On the one hand, the hybrid solution with the planning pyramid and on the other hand the prediction models for the three dimensions quality, energy and maintenance were discussed. In the further course of the project, the plant performance models with regard to energy and maintenance will be examined with an extension of the production data in connection with further approaches. In addition, the concrete integration of these results from the forecasts into the scheduler will be a decisive step towards the end of the project.

Abbreviations

DEC	Deep Embedding Clustering
EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Programming
MOO	Multi-Objective Optimization
RFCS	Research Fund for Coal and Steel

Acknowledgment

The research described in the present paper has been developed within the project entitled "Refinement of production scheduling through dynamic product routing, considering real-time plant monitoring and optimal reaction strategies (DynReAct)" (G.A. No 847203), which was funded by Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS) of the European Union (EU). The sole responsibility of the issues treated in the present paper lies with the authors; the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. We wish to acknowledge with thanks the EU for the opportunity granted that has made possible the development of the present work. We also wish to thank all partners of the project for their support and the fruitful discussion that led to successful completion of the present work.

References

- [1] Branca, T. A.; Fornai, B.; Colla, V.; Murri, M. M.; Streppa, E.; Schröder, A. J.: The Challenge of Digitalization in the Steel Sector; *Metals* 10(2), 2020, P. 288
- [2] Schumpp, F.; Birenbaum, C.; Schneider, M.: Studie – Digitalisierung im Branchenfokus Stahl- und Metallhandel; Fraunhofer IPA, 2019

[3] Iannino, V.; Colla, V.; Maddaloni, A.; Brandenburger, J.; Rajabi, A.; Wolff, A.; Ordieres, J.; Gutierrez, M.; Sirovnik, E.; Schirm, C.; Müller, D.: Improving the flexibility of production scheduling in flat steel production through standard and AI-based approaches: challenges and perspectives; *Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations*, 2021, P. 1-15

[4] Suri, R.; Fu, B.R.: On using continuous flow lines to model discrete production lines; *Discrete Event Dynamic Systems*, 1994, No. 4, P. 129 - 169

[5] Brandenburger, J.; Colla, V.; Cateni, S.; Vignali, A.; Ferro, F.; Schirm, C.; Melcher, J.: Applying big data concepts to improve flat steel production processes; In: S. S. Roy et al. (eds.), *Big Data in Engineering Applications*, Studies in Big Data 44, Springer Singapore, 2018, P. 1–20

[6] Brandenburger, J.; Schirm, C.; Melcher, J.: Instant interactive analysis – How visualisation can help to improve product quality; *Surface Inspection Summit SIS.EUROPE*, Aachen, Germany, 2016

[7] Strobl, C.; Malley, J.; Tutz, G.: An introduction to recursive partitioning: Rationale, application, and characteristics of classification and regression trees, bagging, and random forests; *Psychol. Methods*, vol. 14, 2009, No. 4, P. 323-348

Copyright

Copyright of all material published in the 5th ESTAD 2021 Proceedings passes over to Jernkontoret.